

DOES PLAY AT WORK HELP REDUCE WORKLOAD, INCREASING WELL-BEING? A POST STUDY FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This research focuses on mental leisure activities (games such as crosswords, puzzles and sudoku) to combat fatigue at workplace. One of the aims of this research is to explore the utilisation of these mental games observing the effects on call centre employees. On one hand, mental games are introduced as interventions to stimulate the mind, a form of cognitive load. On the other hand, this mental task is introduced to enhance the mental wellbeing of employees, which is then measured by using a perceived workload scale. In this research NASA rTLX was used to measure perceived workload, prior to this focus group study. This included a four-week intervention study. Participants indicated that well-being was greater for those employees playing the games as compared to those employees who were not playing the games. In addition to this, well-being enhanced as weekend started approaching and employees felt much happier playing the games as the work week ended.

INTRODUCTION

Kazi et al. (2014) has shared that telecom employees spend more time sitting at work, compared to other organizational sectors (see appendix A). Call centre employees, having to sit longer at work, is an indication of non-fatal injuries occurring at workplace. This is evident from the report on non-fatal injuries to employees in Great Britain (see appendix C) (Statistics - Index of tables, 2019). Play in the form of an activity has proven to increase trust among colleagues (Hunter et al., 2010), it enhances group creativity (West et al., 2013), as well as increase in interaction among colleagues. Play at work enhances organizational commitment as well as contributing towards building a friendlier

atmosphere (Sørensen and Spøellestra, 2012). Those organizations which have been keen on the idea of play at work, also accepts the fact that the future is not known (Andersen and Pors, 2014) and hence shows flexibility in making organizational decisions (Pors and Andersen, 2015). Play has also been shown to bring openness in the organizations which increases the intrinsic motivation amongst employees (West et al., 2013).

Mental workload is a broad terminology and can be used by both the specialist ergonomist and the common man in such a way which can fit many contexts. So far researchers and the practitioners in the industry have tried their best to set a benchmark

for measuring workload, however, each time the circumstances have been so varied that this did not seem to be possible (Pickup et al., 2005). According to Ileis et al. (2010), “daily workload is a perceived construct reflecting an employee's perceived work demands on a particular day”. Wickens (2002, p. 161) refers to mental workload as ‘the relation between the(quantitative) demand for resources imposed by a task and the ability to supply the resources by the operator’ (Pickup et al., 2005).

What is important in the discussion here is the relationship between workload and wellbeing at work. There is a growing evidence that increased workload will lead to decreased wellbeing at work (Ileis et al. ,2010) and it is interesting to know how workload can play a part as an indicator of wellbeing. This research will consider perceived mental workload as a part of workplace wellbeing.

Call centre work needs extensive mentally engaging work such as software applications usability, organization, culture, and physical layout. It is suggested that all elements in the environment should be designed and integrated to avoid these problems (Bagnara and Marti, 2001). For this purpose, the task should be known better before it is designed. Some of the points which are important in this regard are task analysis, usability testing, incident analysis and operator training and finally usability testing with operators (Lüdeke, 2012).

Because incremental mental workload can lead to performance deterioration and an increase in perceived workload (Warm et al., 2008), the intention of game playing in this thesis is more towards a fun activity rather than a cognitive load. Regarding games having to contribute to mental effort, there is evidence that video games has an

effect on pre-frontal cortex activity. This happens when one imagines that the body is moving/functioning, the motor cortex takes the responsibility for activation (Han et al., 2010). A person who is playing a game, contributes to some mental effort, nevertheless. For example, a gamer can be asked to do some mental arithmetic, or a gamer can be asked to imagine movement of a geometrical shape. It is good to embed a required mental effort in a game to make the actions of the game look real for the gamer and this also attracts attention from the gamer. Hence, participation in leisure activities has a positive association with cognitive functioning regardless of age, education and socio-economic variables (Wang et al., 2012). Whether mental game playing has a lasting effect on well-being of employees, needs extensive research.

Data collection

The participants were given a case-let, which show cased the results of the perceived workload scores from the experimental study. Three questions were asked from the participants. Each question denoted a broader theme and related concepts were placed under a specific theme. The participants noted points on sticky notes, which were then used for discussion. This method is called free listing. The focus group audit trail is given at appendix B.

Sampling

Regarding focus group discussion, convenience sampling was utilized. Three groups of employees participated in the focus group discussions; the playing group, the non-playing group and the team lead/call centre manager.

Table 1: Members of the call centres who participated in the discussion

Members and location	Players	Non-players	Call centre head/team lead	Total
Focus group 1/York	2	2	2	6
Focus group 2/Leicester	4	4	1	9

Analysis:

Coding for focus group discussion

After the intervention studies, focus group discussions were carried out to find the reasons

for the variations in perceived workload of the call centre employees. A piece of information that was synonymous in ‘meaning’ or ‘feeling’ was put under a broader code. From the discussions, three

themes emerged about the variations in perceived workload. These are evident from table 2. The

table shows the procedure involved in retrieving the themes.

Table 2: Themes and codes for variations in perceived workload

Themes for perceived workload	Codes	No. of references made
Theme 1: Relief on Friday	Endorphins	8
	Weekend approaching	5
	Getting used to game playing	2
Theme 2: Relief in the middle of the intervention	Momentum builds in the middle	8
	Acceptance of games as change	3
	Games as work	3
	No variety of games	2
Theme 3: Relief is greater for players than non-players	Good distraction	8
	Socialization	4
	Jealousy	

The themes in the table are explained further, with the most referenced code explained first.

Theme 1: Relief on Friday

i) Endorphins and weekend approaching

The feelings of happiness as the weekend approached was one of the most common reason why employees thought that the perceived workload reduced on Friday. Employees welcomed the planned schedule that they had in mind for the weekend. The feeling of being happy for the upcoming weekend was overwhelming, which is why the employees felt their perceived workload reduced.

Participant 6 (James): Yesss, so towards the end of the week, you areee I suppose happier and kind of good hormones, I forgot the word

Participant 2: Endorphins

Participant 6: *That’s the word (laughter) Endorphins (and I couldn’t spell it) so it creates, say if your workload was same everyday, actually is how you think about the workload (other participants, ohhhhh, ya)...coz it is coming upto Saturday, you might have a day off, you might be doing something exciting, you might be in a positive frame of mind so you might think lets get this done, might have other things to do’*

Participant 1: Well I think ya, maybe there is something going on the weekend you’ve been waiting for a while so you are excited, you are happier, ya.’

Participant 5: On a Friday we’ll have huddles, where we, kind of given compliments, people win prizes and we

celebrate the week that has been and...you know and stuff, sooo.....we don’t do that on Monday (laughter)’

Participant 4: ‘Because it is the weekend, so people are very happy with the weekend approaching’

Participant 1: ‘Volume, Yes, so less contacts coming in so workload again, is reduced, towards the end of the week’

ii) Getting used to game playing

Another reason but having an impact to a lesser extent was that employees ‘settled’ into game playing by the end of the weekend.

Participant 3: *Maybe playing games took a few days to have an effect’.*

Theme 2: Relief in the middle of the intervention

i) Momentum builds in the middle

Popular reason of perceived workload reducing in the middle of the intervention (around week 2-3) given by the employees was that game playing developed momentum in the middle of the intervention.

Participant 2: *Personally, every single day, every moment you need to play you need to play the game. By the second week when you are playing, it gets better’*

Participant 4: *Ya, the first week they are like, ok this is something new, week 2 I understand what I am supposed to be doing now, I am enjoying this, while week 4 they are like ok I am a bit bored of this now, that is probably why, but this is my theory anyway’*

Participant 5: *Yes, so you work into it at the start and then you kind of doing it becomes like a habit and you are used to it and everything and it is all very good and then*

you kind of go why am I continuing to do this coz it is ending'

ii) Acceptance of games as change

It was highlighted by the employees that the first week was utilized to absorb the game playing, while the end week served to be the finishing week so the employees felt most comfortable in the middle of the weeks where they accepted games as change. Another close factor to this one was the difficulty in acceptance of games as something fun to do.

'Participant 6: So I think you can; both playing games and being told to have fun, it is very difficult, it is as someone saying smile, it's really hard, so for me the technique of the day will be to get the head around people first to enjoy it and secondly you are allowed to enjoy it, then it becomes a fun thing to do and then whilst it's ending, becomes normal'

'Participant 1: Well maybe at the beginning they just have to do it because that's the condition applied to them but it wasn't natural, then after a few weeks they actually enjoyed the games, like ooh, right I'm going to do this, that's funny or you know, not because they have to do it but just because they like doing it'

iii) Games as work

Another interesting aspect was that participants felt that games were taken as an extra piece of work, until they were felt as a norm by the 2nd or 3rd week.

'Participant 2: That's kind of where I'd put the volume low (referring to call volume) because it varies for the week and volume and how much stuff you've got to do so if I were playing the games and people might have felt that it added to the volume of what we were working on, I don't know if that make sense'

'Participant 3: In other way, it could be stressful as well because, no it should, because you have to do something in your break'

i) No variety of games

Participants also indicated towards the fact that there wasn't a big pool of games to choose from so there was less variety of games.

'Participant 2: I enjoyed for the first week and then towards the end, it was a bit boring because I was playing the same game repeatedly'

Theme 3: Relief is greater for players than non-players

i) Good Distraction

Game players felt more relieved because they stated that playing games was an experience which made them feel better and distracted in a good way. According to the participants, it provided them with the opportunity to experiment with something unique.

'Participant 7: Probably when you are playing games, might take off your mind from work coz if you are on a break and you are constantly talking about work, you are not giving your mind a break, you are constantly thinking what am I going to do next'

'Participant 4: I wasn't playing the games but I thought of the people that were playing the games that they might have enjoyed them like break from work to do something mentally different, like fidgeting with the phone, going for a sick break, something different'

'Participant 6: Ahhhh, I think that's mine, so something different to think about so I'd think like you might have gone on your break but you might still have a customer ringing after your break, so you are thinking about that customer during your break so it is a distraction, so it is not a proper break where you are not thinking about your job otherwise if you are (distracted) it is not really a proper break'

'Participant 3: Well if you put more activities, if you've got two activities during the day and you've got extra two so more things to do so less repetition, you know, ya'

ii) Socialization

The game playing also provided the employees an opportunity to bond with one another, which they thought that otherwise they wouldn't have in a normal scheduled work day.

'Participant 1: Some of the games, I had to ask for help because they were all in English so sometimes I had to ask; it's just a way of staying together with your colleagues in the kitchen because they normally are all staring at their phones'

'Participant 5: During the day, just to reiterate, to have a bit of fun and a bit of a laugh but even when you stop playing and you go back out into the floor and stuff, obviously the person, the one that can still imp you about the fact that you lost and everything like that and that you kind of have this banter during the course of the day, I'm

not saying anybody did that to Ashley, its just different form of conversation. You're just talking about something different, other than you know the customer that you had on or the bit of work that you need to do'

iii) Jealousy

Because non players could not play the games, they felt jealous as compared to the players.

'Participant 2: They might be jealous of the other people playing games and they might have felt the envy, oh they are playing games, that is not fair and people who are playing games are really happy and like they are playing games and I'm answering the call, they were really jealous coz they weren't able to play the games'

Discussion

Working life has evolved to be substantially different over time. In the era of 'specialization', individuals strive for paid employment so that they can purchase elements of sustenance (Rose, 2007). This kind of protestant work ethic has made room for individuals to have financial benefits of paid employment. This enables them to fulfil their basic needs, as well as serve as a beneficial member of the society (Cooke et al., 2013). Paid work has a great influence on an individual's self-esteem; the thought that they can achieve success even if the conditions are adverse (Warr 2007). Literature supports the notion that employment is generally good for health and well-being (Waddell and Burton 2006).

With some positive outcomes associated with work-life, there are also adverse effects. Working conditions are different for different job categories and hence the risk level varies for different sectors such as hospitality, agriculture and transport which is

particularly at risk (Jettinghoff and Houtman 2009). There are differences between countries, for example, countries in eastern and western Europe were subject to longer working hours and adverse conditions when compared to central and northern Europe (Wallace et al., 2007). There have been industries and organizations that have considered various working conditions to improve them, when compared to its counterparts with the same constraints (Muñoz de Bustillo et al., 2011). There will always be room for improvement regarding working conditions of any employee. The greater challenge now is that it is very hard to define a good job (Burchell et al., 2013). Another difficulty rises in measuring the components of the good job, even if they are defined. The fact that workers have different preferences, abilities and personality characteristics (Warr 2007), compounds this challenge.

When a job mismatch occurs, it questions, where did everything go wrong? Because these mismatches may cost the employer by increase in turnover rate, they have added additional personality testing and non-work-related abilities and behaviour, as a part of the recruitment test (Robertson and Smith 2001; Carless 2009). From the discussion so far, one can say that it is important that the well-being of an employee is not compromised. At the same time, the job will be considered good for the employer if it also contributes to the productivity (Constable et al., 2009) and a change can only be expected if the return on investment is considered favourable (Miller and Haslam 2009). The two outcomes of the good job, therefore, involves well-being and productivity.

Figure 1: Percentage of employees showing short sickness absence due to health problems (Melrose et al., 2007)

Figure 1 shows that the highest percentage for short sickness absence are headaches. The report does not indicate if the headache is due to physical strain or mental strain, nevertheless one cannot ignore the mental strains associated with headaches and hence organizations are encouraged to add some other mental activity during the breaks.

Limitations

The results are aggregated from a previous intervention study, which was four weeks long. A longitudinal study with pre and post tests can provide further results in this regard, which can open avenues to other areas of employee well-being.

Conclusion

Mental games can play a vital role in reducing perceived workload of employees. When combined with other activities, and reducing/increasing the time associated with playing games, can provide useful insights into improving well-being of employees.

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Appendix A

Bar chart displaying median sitting times (minutes) reported on a workday in each domain across each organizational sector.

Source: (Kazi et al., 2014)

Appendix B

Appendix C

Table 3: Non-fatal injuries to employees in Great Britain, by detailed industry 2014/15-2018/19p
 Source: *Reporting of Injuries, Diseases and Dangerous Occurrences Regulations (RIDDOR)*

SIC 2007 code ⁽¹⁾	Industry	Number of reported non-fatal injuries to employees		
		Total reported non-fatal injury	Of which... Specified	Over-7-day
J (50-63)	Information and communication	437	139	298
58	Publishing activities	16	6	10
59	Motion picture, video and television programme production, sound recording and music publishing activities	51	27	24
60	Programming and broadcasting activities	59	11	48
61	Telecommunications	255	69	186
62	Computer programming, consultancy and related activities	21	9	12

(Source: Hse.gov.uk, 2019)

